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How the temperature and size of A cation govern the structure and bandgap of Zr-based chalcogenide perovskites: Insights from ML accelerated AIMD

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The effects of temperature and composition on the structural and electronic properties of chalcogenide perovskite (CP) materials $AZrX_3$ ($A=Ba, Sr, Ca$; $X=S, Se$) in distorted perovskite (DP) phase have been investigated using ab-initio molecular dynamics accelerated by machine-learned force fields. Long-range van der Waals (vdW) interactions, incorporated into the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) exchange correlation functional using the DFT-D3 scheme, are shown to be crucial for achieving correct predictions of structural parameters. An increase in the size of the A site cations is shown to reduce distortion of structure with respect to the parent cubic (C) phase, realised in the form of inter-octahedral tilting. The previously reported (J. Matter. Chem. C 2022, 10, 12032-12042) gradual transformation of DP to C phase with increasing temperature is shown to be strongly composition dependent. The transformation temperature decreases with the size of cation A and increases with the size of anion X. Thus, within the range of temperatures considered here (300 - 1200 K), a complete transformation was observed only for $BaZrS_3$ (~ 600 K), $SrZrS_3$ (~ 1200 K) and $BaZrSe_3$ (~ 900 K). The computed band gap of CPs is shown to monotonically decrease with increasing temperature and the magnitude of this decrease is found to be proportional to the degree of thermally induced internal structure changes.

1 Introduction

The search for efficient and economic solar cells and optoelectronic materials is growing. With their promising efficiency and inexpensive fabrication, mixed halide perovskites received enormous attention in the scientific community¹⁻⁶ but lead toxicity and instability to withstand real environmental conditions represent major challenges for their effective application.^{7,8} However, chalcogenide perovskites (CP) have been recognised as alternatives with a head start in key prerequisites used to evaluate optoelectronic materials, such as efficiency, exceptional stability as compared to their halide counterpart, and low toxicity.⁹⁻¹¹ These appealing properties of CPs motivated a number of experimental investigations on the synthesis, and electronic and optical properties.¹²⁻¹⁴ Several CPs have been successfully synthesised using high temperature sulphurization of their oxide counterparts.^{15,16} Also the computational predictions played a substantial role in the

development of CP materials. More recently, a density functional theory (DFT) based high-throughput computational screening of varied compositions was performed to identify compounds that are thermodynamically stable and analyse their properties.¹⁷⁻¹⁹ Based on their electronic and optical properties, Sun et al.¹⁹ proposed that $CaTiS_3$, $BaZrS_3$, $CaZrSe_3$ and $CaHfS_3$ with DP structure are suitable for single junction solar cells. Meng et al.²⁰ suggested compositions such as $BaZrSe_3$ and $BaZr_{1-x}Ti_xS_3$ exhibit an optimal bandgap with a theoretical efficiency of 30% but such compositions with desired bandgaps have not been realized experimentally yet. Both the experimental and computational investigations suggest that ABX_3 chalcogenides procure different crystal structures with different connectivity of BX_6 octahedra. The most relevant phases are the $GdFeO_3$ -type structure, also commonly known as distorted perovskite (DP), and the nonperovskite NH_4CdCl_3 -type structure, also called needle (NL) phase.

Many of these reports on high-throughput material screening have the drawbacks of compromising accuracy due to the number of compositions taken into consideration and the neglect of finite-temperature effects. In real situations, temperature plays a key role in driving phase transitions and structural distortions, especially for the perovskite structure²¹⁻²⁴. Structural changes caused by thermal vibrations can significantly affect the physical and electronic properties of a material, such as thermodynamic

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stability, band gap, conductivity, etc. Predicting and understanding these changes is an important prerequisite for the effective use of these materials in practical applications. Accurate modelling of the thermal properties is also very valuable for identifying appropriate experimental conditions for the preparation of materials with specific crystal structures and electronic properties. Such thermal effects have been observed and systematically studied for halide perovskites.^{21,25–30}

The understanding of the influence of temperature on the behaviour of different compositions of CPs is, however, very limited.³¹ In our previous report³², we began to address this deficiency by performing a theoretical investigation of the finite temperature properties of a representative CP material, SrZrS₃. To this end, a series of ab initio molecular dynamics simulations (AIMD) in the NPT ensemble, accelerated by machine learning, were performed. It was found that the distorted perovskite (DP) phase undergoes a gradual conversion of the DP phase into the undistorted parent cubic (C) phase upon heating. As a consequence, a reduction in electronic bandgaps by ~ 0.8 eV was observed for this phase over the temperature range 300–1500 K, with the band gap (E_g) shifting closer to the optimal photovoltaic range as the temperature increases. Based on this analysis, similar effects were anticipated to also be observed for other Zr-based CPs in their DP phase, mainly the series AZrX₃ (A=Ba, Sr, Ca), (X=S, Se). Our preliminary investigations based on static calculations³² suggested that different CP compositions will undergo the DP to C transformation at distinctly different temperatures and therefore also their E_g dependence on T is likely to be different.

In this work, we use our established simulation protocol to conduct a comprehensive investigation and screening of temperature-dependent properties of a series of AZrX₃ (A=Ba, Sr, Ca), (X=S, Se) compositions. Furthermore, several computational studies have shown that dispersive interactions are crucial in determining the lattice constants and mechanical properties of halide perovskites as they alter the energetics and geometry of the crystal.^{33–35} For instance, as reported by Li et al.³⁴, the stabilisation of the inorganic framework and organic components in hybrid organic-inorganic halide perovskite is indirectly affected by vdW interactions, resulting in smaller unit cell volumes and lattice constants than predicted by the semilocal functional PBE. Hence, in this study, we employ van der Waals (vdW) corrected AIMD simulations to examine the importance of long-range dispersion interactions on the structural parameters and consequently their effect on the electronic bandgaps. Investigation of various factors that affect the properties of the selected series of CPs is reported. The role of relative sizes of constituent cations and anions on the structure and bandgap of the series of compositions is discussed. In-house experimental investigations, mainly the HTXRD (High temperature X-ray diffraction) characterizations, have also been performed to corroborate our theoretical predictions on structural phase transformation at high temperatures.

This paper is organised as follows: The outline of the model systems and the computational details of the methodology used in this work are described in Section 2, role of vdW corrections on structural predictions of CPs is discussed in Section 3.1, followed by Section 3.2 wherein the factors influencing the band gap of

CPs are analysed. In Sections 3.3 and 3.4, we explore the thermal effects on the structure and the electronic band gap, respectively. A summary of the most important results is provided in Section 4.

2 Methods and Materials

2.1 Computational methods

The results presented in this study were obtained using the periodic density functional theory (DFT) in the projector-augmented wave (PAW)³⁶ method of Blöchl³⁷, as implemented in the Vienna Ab initio Simulation Package (VASP)^{38,39}. Generalised gradient approximation (GGA) with Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) parameterisation⁴⁰ was used for the exchange-correlation functional. A kinetic energy cutoff of 400 eV was placed on the plane-wave basis set and the electronic energies converged to self-consistency with an accuracy of 10^{-6} eV/cell. A positive uniform background charge has been considered in calculations of hypothetical negatively charged systems discussed in Section 3.2. To account for vdW interactions, dispersion corrections were employed using the zero damping DFT-D3 method proposed by Grimme et al.^{41,42}

Building on the inferences drawn from the previous report³², we focus here on the most relevant phase of each of the ABX₃ compositions, which is the distorted perovskite (DP) phase that can gradually transform into the cubic phase (C) upon heating (see Fig. 1). The relation between the lattice geometries of the DP and C phases is explained in Sec. SI of Supporting Information (ESI). In structural optimizations, carried out using the external optimizer GADGET⁴³, primitive unit cells for DP and C structures, consisting of 20 atoms, respectively, have been used. Brillouin zone of these unit cells was sampled by a Γ -centered mesh of $4 \times 4 \times 4$ k -points. All structures were relaxed until the maximum components of forces acting on atoms were smaller than $5 \cdot 10^{-3}$ eV/Å.

The ab initio molecular dynamics (AIMD) in the NPT ensemble at zero pressure and temperatures of 300 K, 600 K, 900 K, and 1200 K were performed with the supercells constructed as $2 \times 2 \times 2$ multiples of conventional cell of the DP structure. The atomic positions and lattice parameters were treated as dynamical variables. The simulation temperature was maintained using a Langevin thermostat^{44,45} with a friction coefficients of 2 ps^{-1} and 10 ps^{-1} for atoms and lattice degrees of freedom, respectively. The pressure was controlled by a Parrinello-Rahman barostat^{46,47} whereby the mass associated with the lattice degrees of freedom was set to 2 amu. The velocity Verlet algorithm with a time step of 3 fs was used to integrate the equations of motion of the ions. Consistent with the setting used in relaxations, the k -points grid was set to $2 \times 2 \times 2$ in all MD simulations.

In order to accelerate the MD simulations, the machine-learned force field (MLFF) was employed, as recently implemented in VASP^{48,49}. For the description of machine-learned potential energy surface, descriptors based on Gaussian representation of atomic distribution^{49,50} were used. The predicted target properties, i.e, energies, forces and stress tensor components, were obtained via Bayesian linear regression, allowing for reliable es-

Fig. 1 Conventional unit cell of distorted perovskite (DP) phase (a, c) and cubic (C) phase (b, d) of chalcogenide materials ABX_3 . Perspective (above) and top (below) views are shown. The navy blue, grey and orange spheres represent the A cation, the B cation and the X anion, respectively.

timization of the quality of predictions^{48,51}. A separate training procedure was executed for each composition and temperature considered. Post training, a production run of the length of ~ 3 ns was performed at the MLFF level.

After obtaining the production data from the MLFF-MD simulations, an appropriate length of equilibration was chosen based on statistical Mann-Kendall tests⁵² and the corresponding data were discarded. The basic observables such as the lattice parameters or volume have been computed as simple averages over the NPT ensemble. The corresponding standard error was calculated using the blocking method⁵³. Linear and volume expansion coefficients have been determined via

$$\alpha_X(T) = \frac{1}{\langle X \rangle_{T_{ref}}} \left(\frac{d\langle X \rangle}{dT} \right)_{p,T}, \quad (1)$$

where $\langle \dots \rangle$ stands for the ensemble average of cell volume or length of a cell vector (X), T_{ref} was set to 300 K and the differentiation was performed analytically on a third order polynomial fit of the $\langle X \rangle$ vs. T dependence. The calculation of temperature dependent band gaps is detailed in Section. 3.4 The calculation of densities of states (DOS) and crystal orbital Hamilton population (COHP) was performed using the program LOBSTER^{54–56}. All the figures of structures presented in this work were created using the VESTA program⁵⁷.

2.2 Experimental methods

2.2.1 Materials

$BaZrS_3$ and $SrZrS_3$ were prepared by mixing an appropriate ternary oxide, sulfur at a slight excess of boron in the agate mortar, which were loaded into a quartz tube with the inner diameter of 15 mm. The tube was evacuated to 2 Pa and flame sealed. The sample was placed in a tube furnace and kept heated at 1270 K for 36 hours. The typical heating ramp rate was 5 K/min with the holding time 5 hours at 573 K and 873 K and the cooling rate was 5 K/min. After the cool down, the ampules were opened at ambient conditions. The product removed from the reaction ampule was transferred into a beaker and sonicated for 10 min with a small amount (~ 20 ml) of HPLC grade methanol to remove any soluble byproducts (e.g. B_2O_3).

2.2.2 HTXRD measurements

High temperature XRD measurements were performed on Panalytical Empyrean diffractometer coupled with Anton Paar high-temperature chamber HTK-16 N using Pt heating strip in air and in the N_2 atmosphere. The heating rate during non-isothermal segments in which the patterns were collected was 10 min. The temperature step for collecting the individual patterns was 20 K. Rietveld analysis for lattice parameters determination was done using HighScore plus on scans with 2θ ranging from 15° to 55° with a step of 0.026° .

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Effect of long-range dispersion interactions on the CP structure

It follows from the results presented in our previous work³² and also in other reports⁵⁸ that the PBE functional tends to slightly overestimate the lattice parameters of $SrZrS_3$ and other CPs^{20,58}. The likely reason for this problem is incorrect treatment of long range dispersion (vdW) interactions by semilocal functionals^{59,60}. Indeed, several computational studies demonstrated a crucial role of dispersive interactions for correct predictions of the structure, mechanical properties and energetics of halide perovskites.^{33–35} In this section we examine the performance of the Grimme's D3^{41,42} correction to PBE functional. Albeit several more sophisticated vdW correction schemes are available in the literature^{61–64}, the D3 method has a comparative advantage of being one of the most CPU effective schemes (and hence suitable for the use in MD simulations) while yielding a good accuracy for a wide range of materials⁶⁵.

In order to compare the lattice geometries computed in relaxations, effectively corresponding to $T=0$ K simulations, with known experimental results available for $CaZrS_3$, $SrZrS_3$, $BaZrS_3$ and measured at room temperature, we extrapolated the latter to 0 K. To this end, the thermal expansion coefficients determined in our finite-T calculations presented in Section 3.3 were used. Note that it follows from the comparison of our results obtained for $SrZrS_3$ with and without correction³² that the vdW interactions have negligible effect on the result of extrapolation. On average, the uncorrected PBE overestimates the lattice parameters and vol-

Fig. 2 Illustration demonstrating transversal displacement (u_T) of X (yellow) atoms in the middle of the Zr-Zr link from its ideal position in undistorted phase to its corresponding distorted one.

ume of the sulfide series of CPs with DP structure by 1.0 % and 3.1 %, respectively, see Table 1. The inclusion of the D3 correction leads to a systematic reduction in lattice parameters and volume, yielding predictions with a significantly lower mean absolute errors (0.5 % and 1.4 % for the cell parameters and the cell volume, respectively). We notice that the quality of the PBE+D3 predictions worsens slightly with the increasing size of the cation A: while the error in V for CaZrS_3 is only 0.8 %, the value computed for BaZrS_3 is 2.0 % higher compared to experiment.

The dispersion interactions also tend to increase distortion of the DP structures with respect to the parent cubic structures, again making the predictions closer to experiment, which is obvious, e.g., from a slight increase of the transversal displacement (u_T , see Fig. 2) of X atoms from the ideal position in the middle of the Zr-Zr link, see Table 1). As it is clear from the data presented in Table 2, the level of distortion in relaxed distorted CP structures, as measured by u_T , correlates with the stabilization with respect to the parent C phase. The effect of inclusion of D3 on the structure of the selenide CP series is similar in magnitude as for their sulfide counterparts. However, since the experimental data are presently not available for these compounds, the quality of our theoretical predictions can not be evaluated.

Because the inclusion of the D3 correction increases the relative stability of the DP phase with respect to the C phase by 46-163 meV/f.u. see (Table 2), which is related to increase in distortion of the framework discussed above, one can expect that it will affect also the temperature ($T_{DP \rightarrow C}$) at which the thermally induced DP to C transition is completed. Due to the quasi-continuous nature of this transformation³², a rough estimate of $T_{DP \rightarrow C}$ can be made by equating the potential energy difference between the relaxed C and DP ($\Delta E_{DP \rightarrow C} = E(C) - E(DP)$) phase and kinetic energy of an NVT ensemble expressed via equipartition principle ($K = \frac{3}{2}Nk_B T$). The dispersion interactions are predicted to increase the transition temperature by $\sim 70 - 250$ K. Due to the relation between the magnitude of distortion and relative stabilization of DP structures with respect to their cubic counterparts, the predicted transition temperatures also correlate with u_T determined for relaxed CPs. As evident for the values presented in Table 1, the transition temperature is expected to decrease with

Fig. 3 Comparison of temperature dependent scaled lattice parameters obtained from PBE (indicated by dashed line) and PBE+D3 (indicated by bold lines) calculations for SrZrS_3 . Note that the transformation used to obtain the scaled parameters are: $a' = a/\sqrt{2}$, $b' = b/2$, $c' = c/\sqrt{2}$, whereby identity $a' = b' = c'$ holds in the case of undistorted cubic phase. This is indeed the case at 1200 K, where both the DP and the pseudo-C phase coexist.

size of the cation A and the values determined for the selenide series are ~ 200 -300 K higher compared to those computed for their sulfide counterparts.

Finally, we analyze the effect of the inclusion of the long-range interactions in the finite-temperature simulations of SrZrS_3 for which the PBE results have been reported in our previous work³² (a detailed PBE+D3 level analysis of thermal effects on the sulfide and selenide series for CPs is presented in Section 3.3). Fig. 3 compares scaled lattice parameters obtained in NPT MD simulations performed at PBE and PBE+D3 levels for the T range between 0 and 1200 K (the 0 K result corresponds to the result of static relaxation). As expected from the relaxations, the PBE+D3 values are systematically shifted towards lower values (see Table S1). Nevertheless, the two sets of curves are nearly parallel, with deviation in thermal expansion coefficients being within ~ 10 % (see Table S1 in Supporting Information). At 1200 K, which is the highest temperature considered in this work, a phase transition takes place, which is evident from clear discontinuous changes (see Fig. S2 in Supporting Information) in lattice parameters. The fact that the average lattice parameters scaled as $a' = a/\sqrt{2}$, $b' = b/2$, $c' = c/\sqrt{2}$ are identical after this transformation suggests that the newly formed structure corresponds to the cubic phase for which the identity $a' = b' = c'$ holds true (see Fig. S1 and S2). Naturally, the structural changes due to the phase transition affect also the internal geometry of SrZrS_3 . This can be seen from the radial distribution function computed for the Zr-S ($\text{RDF}_{\text{Zr-S}}$) atoms, where the initially well-resolved next-nearest neighbour peaks centered at $r \approx 5.1$ and ≈ 6.0 Å tend to merge into a single broad band at ~ 5.6 corresponding to the next-nearest Zr-S in a perfect cubic structure as T is increased (see Fig. 4). A similar behaviour is observed also for the Sr-S pairs (Figs. S8-S9 in Supporting Information). Although the scaled lattice parameters determined for 1200 K can be considered identical within the uncertainty of our simulations ($a' = 4.799$ Å, $b' = 4.796$ Å, $c' = 4.799$

Fig. 4 Comparison of radial distribution functions (RDF) obtained for SrZrS_3 at 300 and 1200 K from the simulations performed at the PBE (indicated by dashed line) and PBE+D3 (indicated by bold lines) levels. RDF obtained for $T = 1500$ K at the PBE level is also shown as example of the distribution after a complete transformation to the cubic phase.

\AA), it is clear from the the shape of $\text{RDF}_{\text{Zr-S}}$ and a non-vanishing value of transversal displacement of S atoms determined for averaged Cartesian coordinates ($u_T = 0.59 \text{ \AA}$) that the transition to C is not complete at 1200 K. A visual inspection of the structure averaged over whole MD run reveals that the internal structure of this pseudo-C phase resembles that of the tetragonal phase, albeit the cell geometry and volume are distinctly different (see Fig. S1). As shown in our previous work³², both the undistorted cubic lattice geometry and internal structure is achieved at 1500 K. Importantly, the similarity in $\text{RDF}_{\text{Zr-S}}$ obtained at both levels of theory for the extreme temperatures considered in this work (i.e., 300 and 1200 K), demonstrated in Fig. 4, indicates that, besides a slight shortening of the beyond-nearest-neighbor distances related to overall reduction in lattice parameters, the D3 dispersion correction has only a small effect on the internal structure of SrZrS_3 .

3.2 Factors influencing the band gap of DPs

For the purposes of further discussion, it is useful to analyse the main factors influencing the electronic structure of CPs. These involve (i) the charge transfer from A to ZrX_3 , (ii) the volume expansion, and (iii) the distortion of the ideal cubic framework. To disentangle the contributions of these strongly intertwined factors, we analyse DOS and COHP for a series of hypothetical structures, for which the individual effects are well defined. Since, at this stage, we only aim at a qualitative analysis, the electronic structure calculations presented here are restricted to computationally efficient PBE+D3 method, which suffices to capture all the essential trends discussed. For brevity, only the AZrS_3 systems are discussed, nevertheless, most of our conclusions apply also for the AZrSe_3 CPs.

We start our analysis by considering the neutral undistorted cubic structure ZrS_3 without any cation A (system i). The cell vectors compatible with the DP setting were used, whereby the

Fig. 5 Total and partial density of states projected over S and Sr atoms in a) system i - neutral cubic structure $[\text{ZrS}_3]^0$ with no A cation, b) system ii - a hypothetical system $[\text{ZrS}_3]^{-2}$ with undistorted cubic structure, c) system iii - $[\text{ZrS}_3]^{-2}$ with the cell geometry and atomic positions fixed at those from the relaxed DP phase of SrZrS_3 , d) system iv - cubic $[\text{ZrS}_3]^{-2}$ structure with a cell volume of 692.8 \AA^3 obtained from unconstrained relaxation of distorted structure, e) system v - cubic SrZrS_3 with the cell volume 468.9 \AA^3 and f) system vi - relaxed distorted structure of SrZrS_3 .

Table 1 Lattice constants (a , b , c), cell volume per formula unit (V_1), and transversal displacements of the X atoms determined for DP phase of $AZrX_3$ ($A=Ba$, Sr , Ca ; $X=S$, Se) compositions relaxed with PBE and PBE+D3 methods. The relative error (in %) in computed lattice parameters and V_1 with respect to the experimental reference is given in parentheses.

compound	method	a (Å)	b (Å)	c (Å)	V_1 (Å ³ /f.u.)	u_T (Å)
CaZrS ₃	exp. ¹³ (298 K)	7.030	9.590	6.587	110.2	0.858
	exp. ¹³ (0 K)	7.015	9.552	6.551	108.9	0.870
	PBE	7.071 (0.78)	9.644 (1.17)	6.576 (0.38)	112.1 (3.13)	0.857
	PBE+D3	7.023 (0.11)	9.574 (0.22)	6.531 (-0.31)	109.8 (0.83)	0.870
SrZrS ₃	exp. ¹³ (298 K)	7.108	9.766	6.735	117.0	0.706
	exp. ¹³ (0 K)	7.098	9.725	6.698	115.7	0.721
	PBE	7.167 (1.00)	9.827 (1.07)	6.784 (1.33)	119.4 (3.37)	0.709
	PBE+D3	7.121 (0.32)	9.762 (0.37)	6.746 (0.72)	117.2 (1.30)	0.725
BaZrS ₃	exp. ¹³ (298 K)	7.060	9.981	7.025	123.8	0.451
	exp. ¹³ (0 K)	7.075	9.941	6.962	122.5	0.490
	PBE	7.165 (1.26)	10.051 (1.11)	7.050 (1.28)	126.9 (3.76)	0.484
	PBE+D3	7.149 (1.06)	10.000 (0.60)	6.987 (0.33)	124.9 (1.96)	0.514
CaZrSe ₃	PBE	7.402	10.086	6.847	127.8	0.935
	PBE+D3	7.351	10.004	6.783	124.7	0.954
SrZrSe ₃	PBE	7.519	10.269	7.041	135.9	0.797
	PBE+D3	7.456	10.188	7.001	132.9	0.815
BaZrSe ₃	PBE	7.553	10.498	7.289	144.5	0.596
	PBE+D3	7.523	10.431	7.226	141.7	0.628

Table 2 Lattice constants (a , b , c), cell volume per formula unit (V_1), and relative energies with respect to the DP phase ($\Delta E_{DP \rightarrow C}$) for C phase of $AZrX_3$ ($A=Ba$, Sr , Ca ; $X=S$, Se) compositions relaxed with PBE and PBE+D3 methods. The estimated temperatures at which transitions from DP to C phase are completed ($T_{DP \rightarrow C}$) are also shown.

compound	method	a (Å)	b (Å)	c (Å)	V_1 (Å ³ /f.u.)	$\Delta E_{DP \rightarrow C}$ (eV/f.u.)	$T_{DP \rightarrow C}$ (K)
CaZrS ₃	PBE	4.978 (7.040)	(9.956)	(7.040)	123.4	1.420	2197
	PBE+D3	4.958 (7.012)	(9.916)	(7.012)	121.9	1.547	2394
SrZrS ₃	PBE	5.006 (7.079)	(10.011)	(7.079)	125.4	0.704	1089
	PBE+D3	4.987 (7.052)	(9.973)	(7.052)	124.0	0.792	1226
BaZrS ₃	PBE	5.046 (7.136)	(10.091)	(7.136)	128.4	0.162	250
	PBE+D3	5.023 (7.103)	(10.045)	(7.103)	126.7	0.208	322
CaZrSe ₃	PBE	5.219 (7.381)	(10.491)	(7.381)	142.2	1.582	2447
	PBE+D3	5.195 (7.346)	(10.389)	(7.346)	140.2	1.745	2700
SrZrSe ₃	PBE	5.246 (7.418)	(10.446)	(7.418)	144.3	0.880	1361
	PBE+D3	5.223 (7.386)	(10.446)	(7.386)	142.5	0.990	1531
BaZrSe ₃	PBE	5.281 (7.468)	(10.561)	(7.468)	147.3	0.295	456
	PBE+D3	5.258 (7.436)	(10.516)	(7.436)	145.4	0.374	579

cell volume was set to that of the relaxed DP phase of SrZrS₃ (468.9 Å³). As evident from DOS, shown in Fig. 5 (a), the system is metallic. It follows from the partial DOS computed for the S atoms and the COHP projected to nearest neighbours Zr-S and S-S distances that the states near the Fermi level (ϵ_F) are dominated by the S(3p) orbitals, partly involved in the antibonding S-S interactions (Fig. S5 and S6). The states with energy below ϵ_F are hybrids resulting from mixing the S(3p) with Zr(4d) atomic orbitals, whereby the contribution of the latter increases

with decreasing energy. According to the COHP analysis, these hybrid states originate from the bonding Zr-S interactions. The regions of dominant $4d_{xy}$ and $4d_{z^2}$ (the lower part of the valence band) and $4d_{yz}$, $4d_{xz}$, and $4d_{x^2-y^2}$ (the central part of band) states of Zr can be clearly distinguished (Fig. S3). The broad low intensity band of unoccupied states starting at ~ 1.5 eV above ϵ_F is almost exclusively due to the $4d_{yz}$, $4d_{xz}$, and $4d_{x^2-y^2}$ states of Zr. The same Zr(4d) orbitals (with only a modest participation of $4d_{xy}$ and $4d_{z^2}$ orbitals) hybridize with the S(p) states giving rise

Fig. 6 Variation in electronic bandgap as a function of volume for different cations A ($A = \text{Ca}, \text{Sr}, \text{Ba}$) in AZrS_3 in C and DP phases with fixed fractional coordinates of atoms. In the case of C phase, the volume was varied in the interval $\pm 9\%$ around the ground state volume determined for each composition. In the case of DP phase, the volume was varied in the interval $\pm 9\%$ around the ground state volume determined for SrZrS_3 , whereby the lattice geometry was fixed.

to a peak centered at ~ 4.0 eV and the COHP analysis (Fig. S6) shows that these hybrid states are involved in the antibonding Zr-S interactions.

The formal charge of cation A in the AZrX_3 structures is +2, i.e., formally each cation provides two electrons to the system. The effect of this charge transfer can be identified by considering a hypothetical system ZrS_3^{2-} (system ii) that is isostructural with the system i discussed above. Supplementing the extra charge into the system causes only modest changes in the overall shape of DOS and the nature of individual features. Importantly, however, the Fermi level is shifted such that the valence band is fully occupied, see Fig. 5 (b), which is the reason why the system ii exhibits a small but non-vanishing band gap (0.16 eV).

The fact that the antibonding states due to the S-S interactions contribute to the highest occupied states of the ZrS_3^{2-} structure suggests that the system could be stabilized by increasing the S-S distances, e.g., via distortions occurring in the DP phase of the AZrX_3 compounds. In the next step we therefore considered the system ZrS_3^{2-} with the cell geometry and atomic positions fixed at those from the relaxed DP phase of SrZrS_3 (system iii). Compared to the parent cubic structure, the nearest neighbour S-S separations increased from 3.46 to at least 3.59 Å. As evident from COHP (see Fig. S5 in Supporting Information), the valence band contribution of the antibonding S-S interactions was significantly reduced. Compared to the system ii, all five Zr(4d) orbitals now contribute more evenly to both the valence and the conduction band (see Fig. S3), both bands are contracted and the computed band gap increased significantly (from 0.16 eV for system ii to 1.07 eV for system iii). The overall effect of these changes is a relative stabilization of the structure by -0.46 eV/f.u.

In the absence of the A cation, however, the distorted ZrS_3^{2-} structure is unstable. Indeed, the unconstrained relaxation leads to a cubic structure (system iv) with a very large cell volume (692.8 Å³), whereby the total energy lowered by as much as

3.15 eV/f.u. compared to the system ii. This massive increase in volume, leading to elongation of the Zr-S and S-S distances (from 2.44 to 2.78 Å, and from 3.46 to 3.94 Å, respectively), can be viewed as another way of elimination of the antibonding S-S interactions. As in the DOS computed for the system iii (see Fig. 5(c)), an overall contraction of the valence and conduction bands is observed leading to increasing the band gap (0.49 eV) compared to that for the system ii. The nature of the valence and conduction states, however, remains the same as in the system ii.

Next, we compare the cubic SrZrS_3 (system v) with the cell volume of 468.9 Å³ with its counterpart without cation A (i.e., system ii). We emphasize that the only difference between these two systems is the presence of cation A instead of the uniform background charge. The iterative Hirshfeld charge^{66,67} of Sr in SrZrS_3 is 2.02 $|e|$, which is close to the formal charge of cation A in CPs. As shown in Fig. 5 (e) and (f) and S5, S6 (Supporting Information), the shape and the nature of the valence and conduction features of DOS closest to ϵ_F computed for both systems exhibit a striking similarity. This is not only because the amount of charge transferred to ZrS_3 is similar in both cases, but also because the contribution of atomic orbitals of Sr to these states is negligible. The computed E_g of SrZrS_3 in this setting is 0.35 eV, which is not too different from the value of 0.16 eV obtained for ZrS_3^{2-} . Replacing Sr by Ca or Ba in the same structure leads to a very modest change in E_g (the computed values are 0.33 (CaZrS₃) and 0.34 eV (BaZrS₃)), despite somewhat different amounts of charge transferred to ZrS_3 (the iterative Hirshfeld charges of Ca and Ba in these structure are 1.73 and 2.11 $|e|$, respectively). The increase in volume leads to a modest monotonic increase in the band gap as shown in Fig. 6. For SrZrS_3 , E_g increases from 0.19 to 0.49 eV over the interval $\pm 9\%$ around the ground state value and nearly identical dependence is found also for CaZrS₃ and BaZrS₃. This is a remarkable result showing that the cation A affects the band gap of cubic AZrS_3 rather indirectly, via stabilization of low cell volumes through the Coulomb interactions with the ZrS_3^{2-} framework. Indeed, the volumes of relaxed cubic CaZrS₃, SrZrS₃, and BaZrS₃ (487.6, 496.0 and 506.8 Å³, respectively) are all significantly lower compared to that of relaxed ZrS_3^{2-} (692.8 Å³) and their increase with the size of cation A is rather modest.

Relatively small changes in DOS are observed also when replacing the uniform background charge in the system iii by the cation Sr^{2+} (system vi). According to the iterative Hirshfeld analysis, the charge transferred from Sr to ZrS_3 is 2.02 $|e|$, which is, coincidentally, identical to the value determined for the cubic structure discussed above. As in the case of the cubic structure, the band gap computed for the SrZrS_3 (1.22 eV) is larger than that for the analogous system without A (1.07 eV). Replacing Sr by Ca or Ba while fixing the cell and atomic geometry leads, however, to more pronounced variation in band gap ($E_g = 1.27$ eV and 1.11 eV for CaZrS₃ and BaZrS₃, respectively) than observed for the cubic systems (Fig. 6). Still, this result shows that the direct effect of cation of A on band gap, i.e., the decrease in E_g with increasing size of A at fixed structure, is rather modest, whereby, as in the cubic structures, the increase in volume leads to a monotonic increase in the band gap. If only volume is varied (i.e., fractional coordinates of atoms are fixed) over the interval $\pm 9\%$ around the

Fig. 7 Variation in electronic bandgaps as a function of volume for different AZrS₃ (A = Ca, Sr, Ba) compositions in DP phase. The volume was varied in the interval $\pm 9\%$ around the ground state volume determined for each composition, whereby the atomic positions and lattice geometries were relaxed.

ground state value, the band gap of SrZrS₃ increases from 1.10 to 1.27 eV. The curves obtained for the same structures of CaZrS₃ and BaZrS₃ compositions are similarly shaped but, unlike in the case of cubic structures, they are shifted by up to ± 0.1 eV with respect to that for SrZrS₃. As expected, this similarity in shape and position of the E_g versus V dependencies is significantly reduced upon the relaxation of the DP structures (see Fig. 7). This result shows, once again, that the structure of the ZrS₃ framework is the key factor determining the bandgap of AZrS₃ compounds, while the role of cation A is mainly indirect, via its effect on the structure.

3.3 Thermal effects on the crystal structure

In this section we investigate the thermal effects on the AZrX₃ structures using ab initio NPT MD simulations accelerated by MLFF⁴⁹ (see Section 2). The finite temperature values of structural parameters for the DP and C phases are listed in Table 3. In addition, the thermal dependence of the linear and volume thermal expansion coefficients evaluated using equation 1 is presented in Fig. S7 in the Supporting Information.

All the compositions in this study undergo a monotonic and positive volume thermal expansion upon heating. Close to 0 K, the magnitude of volume thermal coefficient is similar for all compositions examined and takes the value of $33\text{-}40 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ (see Fig. S7 in Supplementary Information). The temperature induced changes in the lattice parameters are anisotropic and, as discussed in our previous work,³² they are related to the fact that increased temperature tends to reduce the distortion with respect to the cubic phase, which is eventually restored at a sufficiently high T . Hence, the lattice parameter c with the value deviating more from that in the C phase than a and b (cf. Tables 1 and 2) changes most significantly with T . Interestingly, although the lattice parameters generally elongate upon heating, the overall tendency of distortion reduction with increasing T may also lead to negative expansion in some cases. This is observed for the parameter a in

SrZrS₃ and in SrZrSe₃ at temperatures over 900 K.

At the internal structure level, the tendency to reduce deformation with respect to C upon heating is obvious from the radial distribution function for the Zr-X or A-X pairs, where the initially well resolved next-nearest neighbour peaks tend to merge into a single band (Fig. S8 and S9 of ESI). As a simple measure of progress of the DP \rightarrow C transformation, one can also use u_T computed for averaged Cartesian coordinates (see Table 3), which clearly decreases with T . Although this trend is general, its magnitude depends strongly on the composition of CP. As it is clear from the data presented in Table 3, the magnitude of T -induced reduction of u_T in AZrX₃ increases with the size of A and decreases with the size of X. Thus, BaZrS₃ represents one extreme case, with u_T dropping from 0.51 Å at 0 K to 0.00 Å at 1200 K. The other extreme case is CaZrSe₃ with change in u_T being as small as 0.04 Å (from 0.95 Å to 0.91 Å) within the same temperature interval.

The lower the values of u_T at 0 K (see Tab. 3), the lower the temperature at which the transformation to C is completed. In particular, the compound BaZrS₃ with the low temperature u_T value of 0.51 Å exhibits phase transition between 300 and 600 K, while the transition T for BaZrSe₃ with nominal $u_T=0.63$ Å falls into the interval between 600 and 900 K. Furthermore, as discussed in Sec. 3.1, the lattice geometry of SrZrS₃, which is the compound with the next lowest u_T value at 0 K (0.73 Å) undergoes change corresponding to pseudo-cubic phase at 1200 K, but the RDF evaluated for the Zr-S and Sr-S pairs, as well as the relatively large u_T value indicate that phase transition is not yet fully completed at this point (as shown in our previous work, a full conversion is achieved when T is increased to 1500 K). We note that these results are in qualitative agreement with the transition temperatures estimated from the potential energy differences between relaxed DP and C structures (see Table 2). Thus, although the latter seem to significantly underestimate the actual $T_{DP \rightarrow C}$, the static approach proves to be useful for computationally inexpensive and fast transition temperature estimates.

3.4 Thermal effects on electronic bandgap

Using the structural data generated in our NPT MD runs described in Section 3.3, the temperature dependent band gaps (E_g) were determined as ensemble averages ($\langle E_g \rangle$). To this end, the following procedure was undertaken for all compounds. First, an ensemble of 200 configurations was selected for each simulation temperature and the band gap was computed at the PBE+D3 level. The averaged values ($\langle E_{g,PBE+D3} \rangle$) are listed in Table 4. Since the electronic part of the PBE+D3 method is identical with that of uncorrected PBE functional (indeed, the vdW correction affects E_g only indirectly via the structural changes discussed in Section 3.1), which is known to strongly underestimate E_g of CPs^{19,32}, we determined in the next step of our procedure the ensemble averaged E_g also at the HSE06 level that provides band gaps close to experimental reference.^{19,32} We note, however, that the calculations performed at the HSE06 level are at least 80 times more time consuming than those with the PBE method. In order to reduce the computational cost of determining $\langle E_{g,HSE06} \rangle$,

Table 3 Ensemble averages of lattice constants (a , b , c), cell volume per formula unit (V_1), and transversal displacement of X in averaged structures (u_T) calculated for $AZrX_3$ ($A=Ca, Sr, Ba$; $X=S, Se$) in the temperature range between 0 and 1200 K using PBE+D3 functionals. The symbol (c) indicates the cubic (or pseudo-cubic) phase of the composition for which the values in the parantheses represent the scaled parameters $a' = a/\sqrt{2}$, $b' = b/2$, $c' = c/\sqrt{2}$.

T (K)	a (Å)	b (Å)	c (Å)	V_1 (Å ³ /f.u.)	u_T (Å)
CaZrS₃					
0	7.023	9.573	6.531	109.8	0.870
300	7.038	9.611	6.567	111.0	0.858
600	7.053	9.651	6.605	112.4	0.846
900	7.069	9.694	6.648	113.8	0.831
1200	7.083	9.742	6.692	115.4	0.813
SrZrS₃					
0	7.121	9.761	6.746	117.2	0.725
300	7.131	9.802	6.783	118.5	0.709
600	7.138	9.846	6.827	119.9	0.692
900	7.139	9.899	6.879	121.5	0.665
1200	7.133	9.956	6.942	123.2	
1200 (c)	7.041 (4.979)	9.952 (4.976)	7.041 (4.979)	123.3	0.587
BaZrS₃					
0	7.150	10.001	6.985	124.9	0.514
300	7.135	10.041	7.048	126.2	0.475
600 (c)	7.126 (5.039)	10.069 (5.034)	7.126 (5.039)	127.8	0.087
900 (c)	7.154 (5.059)	10.125 (5.062)	7.154 (5.059)	129.5	0.028
1200 (c)	7.184 (5.080)	10.173 (5.086)	7.184 (5.080)	131.2	0.004
CaZrSe₃					
0	7.350	10.004	6.783	124.7	0.954
300	7.372	10.044	6.821	126.2	0.942
600	7.393	10.087	6.862	127.9	0.928
900	7.414	10.136	6.905	129.7	0.913
1200	7.434	10.186	6.956	131.6	0.910
SrZrSe₃					
0	7.456	10.187	7.003	133.0	0.815
300	7.473	10.229	7.041	134.5	0.800
600	7.486	10.277	7.086	136.2	0.782
900	7.495	10.332	7.137	138.1	0.760
1200	7.495	10.396	7.205	140.3	0.726
BaZrSe₃					
0	7.523	10.431	7.225	141.8	0.628
300	7.516	10.481	7.286	143.5	0.600
600	7.503	10.538	7.355	145.4	0.554
900 (c)	7.480 (5.289)	10.566 (5.283)	7.477 (5.287)	147.7	0.108
1200 (c)	7.513 (5.312)	10.637 (5.318)	7.513 (5.312)	150.0	0.041

we made use of the fact that the $E_{g,PBE+D3}$ and $E_{g,HSE06}$ are strongly linearly correlated (see Section S5 in Supporting Information). We, therefore, performed explicit HSE06 calculations only for 30 out of 200 structures considered in the $\langle E_{g,PBE+D3} \rangle$ calculations for each of two extreme temperatures and used these data to determine the parameters of a linear model that we subsequently employed to determine $E_{g,HSE06}$ for all 200 data points at

each temperature. Our tests performed for SrZrS₃ and presented in Section S5 of Supporting Information show that this approach leads to errors in $\langle E_{g,HSE06} \rangle$ within 0.01 eV.

The T -dependence of band gaps for all compositions is shown in Fig. 9, the corresponding numerical values for both the PBE+D3 and the HSE06 levels of theory are compiled in Table 4. The general trend observed is a monotonic decrease of

Fig. 8 Scaled lattice parameters $a' = a/\sqrt{2}$, $b' = b/2$, $c' = c/\sqrt{2}$ of DP/C form of $AZrX_3$ ($A=\text{Ca, Sr, Ba}$), ($X=\text{S, Se}$) as functions of temperature. Note that the identity $a' = b' = c'$ holds in the case of undistorted cubic phase. Triangle and star symbols represent the theoretical and experimental results, respectively. To facilitate a clearer comparison with theory, which tends to slightly overestimate the lattice parameters (see Table 3), all experimental data points were shifted by 0.02 \AA

Fig. 9 Temperature dependence of the HSE06 electronic bandgaps for DP/C phases of $AZrX_3$ ($A=\text{Ba, Sr, Ca}$; $X=\text{S, Se}$) computed as ensemble averages from NPT MD performed at the PBE+D3 level. The dotted lines define the optimal range of the desired bandgap for photovoltaics⁶⁸.

$\langle E_{g,HSE06} \rangle$ with T . The slope of this dependence increases in absolute value with T in most cases. The exceptions are the compounds BaZrS_3 and BaZrSe_3 undergoing the DP to C transition at $\sim 600 \text{ K}$ and 900 K (see Section 3.3), where also the largest changes in $\langle E_{g,HSE06} \rangle$ occur. At a first sight, the E_g versus T trend seems to be in contrast to analysis provided in Section 3.2, where a small monotonous increase of E_g with volume (monotonously

increasing with T , see Section 3.3) was demonstrated. Hence, based on our analysis from Section 3.2 and in accord with our previous report³², we explain the observed decrease in E_g with T by the internal structure changes due to gradual DP \rightarrow C transition. Indeed, the magnitude of the total band gap decrease over the temperature range considered is largest (0.65 eV) for BaZrS_3 and smallest (0.24 eV) for CaZrSe_3 , the systems with the largest and the smallest temperature-induced reduction in u_T , respectively. From the data presented in Table 4, one can deduce that $|\Delta E_g|$ increases with the size of cation A and decreases with the size of anion X. All the trends predicted by HSE06 are virtually parallel to those from the PBE+D3 calculations, with the $\langle E_{g,PBE+D3} \rangle$ values being downshifted by $0.5\text{-}0.8 \text{ eV}$.

The experimental information on the band gap is presently available only for the $X=\text{S}$ series at the room temperature^{16,31}. Our results are in a very good agreement with these reports, with the error being within 2-8 %. For a fixed finite T , the general tendency is a decrease in the band gap with increase in the size of A and X, with the results for CaZrSe_3 and SrZrSe_3 at 300 K being the only exceptions from this trend. These results are, again, in accord with the conclusion made in Section 3.2. From the data presented in Fig. 9, we conclude that the calculated band gap values fall into the optimal range⁶⁸ of device operation for all compositions of selenides across all temperatures. While the bandgaps of CaZrS_3 and SrZrS_3 are slightly above the desired range, E_g value for BaZrS_3 starts falling in the range beyond 400

Table 4 Ensemble averages of bandgaps calculated for AZrX₃ (A=Ca, Sr, Ba; X=S, Se) in the temperature range between 0 and 1200 K using PBE+D3 and HSE06 functionals. The symbol (c) indicates the cubic (or pseudo-cubic) phase of the composition.

T (K)	$\langle E_{g,PBE+D3} \rangle$ (eV)	$\langle E_{g,HSE} \rangle$ (eV)
CaZrS₃		
0	1.216	2.009
300	1.162	1.964 (1.90 ¹⁶)
600	1.099	1.876
900	1.004	1.742
1200	0.877	1.563
SrZrS₃		
0	1.218	2.016
300	1.152	1.954 (2.00*, 2.05-2.13 ³¹)
600	1.032	1.793
900	0.916	1.636
1200	0.746	1.406
1200 (c)	0.771	1.440
BaZrS₃		
0	1.051	1.830
300	0.935	1.691 (1.81*, 1.73 ¹⁶ , 1.81 ³¹)
600 (c)	0.769	1.434
900 (c)	0.686	1.305
1200 (c)	0.607	1.182
CaZrSe₃		
0	0.765	1.428
300	0.751	1.405
600	0.742	1.388
900	0.692	1.295
1200	0.638	1.192
SrZrSe₃		
0	0.817	1.479
300	0.788	1.469
600	0.740	1.381
900	0.663	1.238
1200	0.594	1.113
BaZrSe₃		
0	0.714	1.372
300	0.704	1.364
600	0.635	1.236
900 (c)	0.504	0.989
1200 (c)	0.475	0.936

K. Since BaZrX₃ (X=S, Se) are commonly and successfully synthesized compositions in laboratory¹⁵, plus they are expected to show early phase transitions to the ideal cubic phase (600 K - 900 K), we anticipate that thermal bandgaps could be potentially tuned by exploring the different combination of mixed BaZrS_{3-x}Se_x compositions.

4 Conclusions

A comprehensive DFT investigation of effect of composition and temperature on the structure and electronic properties of a class of chalcogenide perovskites AZrX₃ (A = Ca, Sr, Ba; X = S, Se)

in distorted perovskite structure was performed. The long range dispersion interactions, introduced by means of the D3 method of Grimme et al.^{41,42}, were shown to improve the quality of zero and finite temperature structural predictions, reducing the average error in lattice parameters and volume for compounds with experimentally known structures (CaZrS₃, SrZrS₃ and BaZrS₃) from 1.0% and 3.1% to 0.5% and 1.4% respectively.

Various factors affecting the electronic band gap of CPs were analysed in detail in a series of zero-T calculations. It was shown that the cation A affects E_g mainly indirectly by influencing the magnitude of distortion in the structure of CP, while its direct effect, identified through the change of E_g for a fixed geometry upon changing A, is only modest (0.01-0.08 eV). For all compositions, a monotonous decrease of band gap with temperature was observed. In contrast, the change of structure from distorted perovskite to cubic leads to large reduction of E_g (by 0.5-0.7 eV), making the underlying structural transformation the key factor dictating trends in band gap changes due to various external stimuli. The importance of the symmetry breaking distortions on the electronic structure was demonstrated also in our previous work³² for the specific case of SrZr₃ and in other reports for related materials^{21,27,28}.

The finite temperature effects on the structure of CPs were investigated using ab initio-quality ML-accelerated molecular dynamics in NPT ensemble. On the temperature range of 0-1200 K considered in this work, monotonous expansion of volume and most of the lattice vectors was observed. All compounds exhibited a tendency to gradually reduce distortion with respect to the parent cubic structure with increasing temperature. The magnitude of this tendency, measured by the parameter u_T , however, was found to be strongly composition dependent, whereby it increases with the size of cation A and decreases with the size of anion X. Thus, BaZrS₃ represents one extreme case for which u_T was reduced from 0.51 Å at 0 K to 0.00 Å at 1200 K, indicating that the DP→C phase transition was complete. The other extreme case is CaZrSe₃, with a very rigid structure for which u_T barely changed (from 0.95 to 0.91 Å) over the same T interval.

The T -dependences of electronic band gaps were computed at the HSE06 level as ensemble averages over the data generated in NPT MD. For all compositions, a monotonic decrease with T was observed, a magnitude of which was dictated by the magnitude of underlying internal structure. Hence, ΔE_g of -0.65 eV and -0.24 eV obtained for BaZrS₃ and CaZrSe₃ represents two extreme cases. The E_g values computed for sulfides series at $T=300$ K are in a reasonable agreement (relative error within 2 - 8 %) with the available experimental data^{16,31}. To the best of our knowledge our predictions for the selenides series represent the only finite- T report as of to date. In contrast to sulfides, the band gaps of selenides computed for a wide range of temperatures (including the room temperature) fall into the optimal range for practical application⁶⁸ (within 0.9-1.6 eV).

Altogether, we demonstrated that the prime thermal effect on the structure of CPs is the change in degree of distortion with respect to the parent cubic phase, which in turn represents the most important factor affecting the magnitude of their band gap. Of course, the degree of such distortions can be controlled also

by other means, e.g., via partial substitutions of cations and/or anions by atoms of different sizes, which we plan to investigate in our future work.

Author Contributions

Namrata Jaykhedkar Investigation, Visualization, Writing- Original draft preparation. **Roman Bystrický** Investigation, Writing- Reviewing and Editing. **Milan Sýkora** Funding acquisition, Project administration, Writing- Reviewing and Editing. **Tomáš Bučko** Conceptualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing- Original draft preparation.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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